

INTERNATIONAL ONLINE TOURISM AND TRAVEL MANAGEMENT

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Abstract:

The Online Travel Booking Services is the modern way of attracting people for the tourism industry. The tourism has become so easy because of this service and there are lots of improvements needed for this industry as whole. There are OTBS functions even for middle class people or salaried person who cannot afford costlier services. So there are few online tourist websites which provide quality service at a cheaper cost which is a great advantage for middle class people. This would increase the revenue of the tourism industry which is in turn an advantage for the government. The more detailed and beautiful websites attracts more tourists as they have a glimpse of what is available in the place and all the details about their travel. So our government should take keen action on developing more services regarding to OTBS which is the future of tourism industry.

Key Words: Travel Booking, Websites & Government

Introduction:

Tourism is travel for pleasure or business; also the theory and practice of touring, the business of attracting, accommodating, and entertaining tourists, and the business of operating tours. Tourism may be international, or within the traveller's country. The World Tourism Organization defines tourism more generally, in terms which go "beyond the common perception of tourism as being limited to holiday activity only", as people "traveling to and staying in places outside their usual environment for not more than one consecutive year for leisure, business and other purposes". Tourism can be domestic or international, and international tourism has both incoming and outgoing implications on a country's balance of payments. Today, tourism is a major source of income for many countries, and affects the economy of both the source and host countries, in some cases being of vital importance.

Objectives of the Study:

- ✓ To study the importance of tourism industry of the world
- ✓ To study the emergence of online tourist booking series
- ✓ To analyse the benefit and difficulties of OTBS
- ✓ To invite the additional services expected by the respondents to make OTBS effective

Scope of Tourism Development:

Tourism is one of the fast growing industry in the world. When considering India, undoubtedly there is an unlimited scope of tourism development in the South Indian state of Kerala which would definitely bring up the economic growth of the country. There is a high degree of widening the service in this industry with the help of technology and infrastructure in connection with the globalisation process. I am going to examine the scope and opportunity of developing the tourism in Kerala, focusing and exploring its natural resources and cultural inheritance and the very traditional nature of simplicity and service. There is quality tourism with Kochi centred resort as the most popular. Kerala is rich in culture with full of colourful and unique art. It is said to be 'God's own Country' and it is the one of the finest tourist spot in the world. Kerala has won the popularity as a tourist spot and became one of the important tourist destinations in the world.

Sampling Technique:

The travel and tourism industry has emerged as an economic force in both the nation and the Tenth Federal Reserve District. Rising incomes, increased leisure time, and declining airfares in the United States and abroad have allowed more and more people to travel in recent decades. This article has shown how the travel and tourism industry performs over time and across areas. At the national level, the industry has consistently outperformed the overall economy during times of expansion and seldom fallen more than the rest of the economy during recessions. Travel and tourism performs somewhat differently in the Tenth District. Specifically, the industry has withstood the effects of the last two recessions much better in the district than in the nation due largely to less reliance on business and international travelers. Many leisure destinations in the district, however, remain highly susceptible to the effects of nature, which can strike at any time

Convenience Sampling:

Convenience sampling (also known as grab sampling, accidental sampling, or opportunity sampling) is a type of non-probability sampling that involves the sample being drawn from that part of the population that is close to hand. This type of sampling is most useful for pilot testing. A convenience sample is a type of non-

probability sampling method where the sample is taken from a group of people easy to contact or to reach. For example, standing at a mall or a grocery store and asking people to answer questions would be an example of a convenience sample. This type of sampling is also known as grab sampling or availability sampling. There are no other criteria to the sampling method except that people be available and willing to participate. In addition, this type of sampling method does not require that a simple random sample is generated, since the only criteria is whether the participants agree to participate

Period of the Study:

The study was conducted for a period of 6 months from September 2017 to February 2018.

Research Methodology:

A research design in the overall plan or program of research. A research design or model indicates a plan of action to be carried out in connection with a proposed research work.

Area of Study:

The area of the study is limited to Coimbatore city. It is popularly known as Manchester of south India, is situated in the western part of the state Tamil Nadu.

Statistical Tools Used:

Percentage Analysis:

This is the simplest way to analysis different types of data in this method percentage rate of each data was found that and with respect to total and with the help of the percentage (%) rate the analyzing the data was carried out

ANOVA:

An ANOVA test is a way to find out if survey or experiment results are significant. In other words, they help you to figure out if you need to reject the null hypothesis or accept the alternate hypothesis. Basically, you're testing groups to see if there's a difference between them.

One Way ANOVA:

A one way ANOVA is used to compare two means from two independent (unrelated) groups using the F-distribution. The null hypothesis for the test is that the two means are equal. Therefore, a significant result means that the two means are unequal.

Source of Variance	Sum of Squares	Degree of Freedom	Mean Square	Variance of F
Between sample	SSC	VI = C-1	MSC = SSC/(c-1)	
Within sample	SSE	V2 = n-c	MSE = SSE/(n-c)	MSC/MSE
Total	SST	n-1		

Review of Literature:

Citation	Sample	Environment	Method	Conclusions
Chris Ryan and Stephen page	500	Theme parks	Interview	Potential of total quality management to improve the competitiveness of tourism
Dr. Prashanta Athma and Ms. Vijaya Lakshmi	400	Andhra Pradesh Travel and Tourism Corporation	Secondary Data	They have concluded their article by quoting Potentials of tourism is vast in Andhra Pradesh but not fully explored though efforts are being made to develop eco tourism.

Analysis and Interpretation:

Age Wise Distribution of the Respondent:

Age	No. of Respondent	Percentage
18-25 Years	22	88%
25-35 Years	3	12%
36-45 Years	0	0%
50 and above	0	0%
Total	25	100

Interpretation:

The above table shows that 88% of the respondents are between the age group of 18-25 years, 12% of the respondents are of the age group of 25-35 years.

Gender of the Respondents:

Gender	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Male	18	72%
Female	7	28%
Total	25	100

Interpretation:

The above table shows that 72% of the respondents are male, 28% of the respondents are female.

Occupation of the Respondents:

Occupation	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Self	19	76
Private	4	16
Government	2	8
Total	25	100

Interpretation:

The above table shows that 8% of the respondents are government employee, 16% of the respondents are private employee, 76% of the respondents are self-persons.

Education Qualifications of the Respondents:

Education Qualifications	No. of Respondents	Percentage
HSC	0	0%
Degree	12	48%
PG	10	40%
Professional	3	12%
Total	25	100

Interpretation:

The above table shows that 0% of the respondents are HSC, 50% of the respondents are Degree, 42% of the respondents are PG, 12% of the respondents are professional.

ANOVA:

Demographic factors (Age, Gender, Country and Occupation) and the frequency of using OTBS:

H0: There is no significant association between Age and the frequency of using OTBS

H0: There is no significant association between gender and the frequency of using OTBS

H0: There is no significant association between country and the frequency of using OTBS

H0: There is no significant association between Occupation and the frequency of Using OTBS

ANOVA						
		Sum of Squares	DF	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Age	Between Groups	.604	3	.201	1.535	.235
	Within Groups	2.756	21	.131		
	Total	3.360	24			
Gender	Between Groups	.256	3	.085	.374	.772
	Within Groups	4.784	21	.228		
	Total	5.040	24			
Occupation	Between Groups	.061	3	.020	.046	.987
	Within Groups	9.379	21	.447		
	Total	9.440	24			
Country	Between Groups	.551	3	.184	.943	.437
	Within Groups	4.089	21	.195		
	Total	4.640	24			

Interpretation:

- ✓ In comparison of Age and Type of organic product, the calculated Value = 1.535
Table Value = 3.072, Calculated Value < Table Value, H0 is accepted.
There is significant Association between Age and frequency of using OTBS
- ✓ In comparison of income and type of using, the calculated value = .374
The table value = 3.072, calculated value < the table value, H0 is accepted
There is significant Association between gender and Frequency of using OTBS
- ✓ In comparison of occupation and type of using, the calculated value = .046
The table value = 3.072, calculated value < the table value, H0 is accepted
There is significant Association between occupation and frequency of using OTBS
- ✓ In comparison of occupation and type of using, the calculated value = .943
The table value = 3.072, calculated value < the table value, H0 is accepted
There is significant Association between country and frequency of using OTBS.

Findings:

- ✓ Majority (72%) of the respondents are male.
- ✓ Majority (88%) of the respondents are between the age group of 18-25 years.
- ✓ Majority (76%) of the respondents are self-employed.
- ✓ Majority (50%) of the respondents are Degree
- ✓ There is significant Association between Age and frequency of using OTBS
- ✓ There is significant Association between gender and Frequency of using OTBS

- ✓ There is significant Association between occupation and frequency of using OTBS
- ✓ There is significant Association between country and frequency of using OTBS
- ✓ There is significant Association between Age and difficulty of using OTBS
- ✓ There is significant Association between gen and difficulty of using OTBS
- ✓ There is significant Association between occupation and difficulty of using OTBS
- ✓ There is significant Association between occupation and difficulty of sing OTBS
- ✓ There is significant Association between Age and difficulty of using OTBS
- ✓ There is significant Association between gender and difficulty of using OTBS
- ✓ There is significant Association between occupation and difficulty of using OTBS
- ✓ There is significant Association between occupation and difficulty of using OTBS.

Suggestions:

- ✓ The OTBS services can be simplified so that anyone can use it freely
- ✓ The awareness of OTBS can be given to everyone
- ✓ Getting the best service tough cheaper price will improve the scope of OTBS
- ✓ Getting more information on the country a person visits would be an added advantage
- ✓ The cheaper and best services would attract even salaried personnel

Conclusion:

The conclusion is that there are OTBS functions even for middle class people or salaried person who cannot afford costlier services. So there are few online tourist websites which provide quality service at a cheaper cost which is a great advantage for middle class people. This would increase the revenue of the tourism industry which is in turn an advantage for the government. The more detailed and beautiful websites attracts more tourists as they have a glimpse of what is available in the place and all the details about their travel. So our government should take keen action on developing more services regarding to OTBS which is the future of tourism industry.

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